

Variants	Natural Site Effect	Cryptic Sites of Interest	Splicing Consequence (donor/acceptor only)	ESE Analysis	Splicing Consequence (ESEs considered)	Experimental Results from Paper	Match to Predictions
BRCA1:c.80+5G>A (exon 2)	8.9 -> 5.8 bits (-3.1 bits; donor) Ri,total: 11.1 -> 8.0 bits	No cryptic sites as strong as weakened cryptic site in region	Leaky, possibly an increase of skipping with residual splicing.	Nothing Significant.	Nothing Significant.	Out of frame exon skipping of exon 2	YES
BRCA1:c.134+5G>T (exon 3)	8.3 -> 5.0 (-3.3 bits; donor) Ri,total: 10.9 -> 7.6 bits	Another 5.0 bit cryptic site 103nt away. Leads to a slightly stronger Ri,total (8.2 vs 7.6 bits).	Leaky, residual splicing, possible exon skipping and cryptic site use leading to a 157bp splice form (natural exon 54bp).	Str: 1.8 -> 4.8 bit (branchpoint) Strengthened (Str): 0.7 -> 4.4 bit (TIA1) Created: 4.2 bit ELAVL1	Exon Def: Inclusion of ELAVL1 increases cryptic Ri,tot while decreasing wt Ri,tot (WT: 10.9 -> 7.6 bits; Cry: 3.3 -> 9.4 bits)	Increase in out of frame skipping of exon 3. No mention of cryptic site use.	YES
BRCA1:c.1878A>G (exon 10)	No change (2.9 bit donor, 9.4 bit acceptor) Ri,total: 1.3 bits	Creates a 4.1 bit donor site (Ri,total 1.6 -> 4.6 bit), giving it a rank of 4th isoform (#1 Ri,total is 6.7 bits)	Cryptic site use may be seen, but would not be dominant form.	Created: 4.3 bit hnRNPH Str: 1.5 -> 4.5 bit SC35 Abolished: 2.4 bit TIA1	Repressor and enhancer created near cryptic site would cause opposing effects. Impact not predictable.	None affected mRNA splicing	YES
BRCA1:c.4115G>A (exon 11)	No change (7.2 bit donor, 8.1 bit acceptor) Ri,total: 15.0 bits	A weak donor strengthened (2.8 -> 3.6 bits)	Wildtype splicing unaffected. Strengthened cryptic site unlikely to be used.	Created: 5.5 bit hnRNP A1 site; Created: 4.3 bit PTB site Str: 1.3 -> 6.0 bit hnRNPH	Exon Def. of hnRNPA1 site shows increase in Ri,total though (15 -> 16.5 bits; strength of site > gap surprisal penalty)	None affected mRNA splicing	YES
BRCA1:c.4186-10G>T (exon 12)	3.1 -> 5.4 bits (+2.3 bits; acc.) Ri,total: 10.0 -> 12.3 bits	2.1 -> 4.4 bits acc. Strengthened 3nt away; Ri,total: 8.9 -> 11.2 bits	WT splice form would dominate. If cryptic site is used, it would be less common than WT splice form. If exon 12 naturally skips, this will reduce as well.	Created: 5.8 bit TIA1 site Str: 3.7 -> 6.0 bit TIA1 Str: 4.0 -> 6.5 bit TIA1 Created: six ELAVL1 sites (strongest is 7.8 bits)	Including ESEs to Ri,total calculations only cause it to increase. Thus, WT splicing is expected to continue to be unaffected.	Did not result in aberrant splicing.	YES
BRCA1:c.4674A>G (exon 14)	4.9 -> 2.4 (-2.5 bits; donor) Ri,total: 16.2 -> 13.7 bits	Pre-existing 2.8 bit site 11nt away is isoform 1: Ri,total: 13.9 bits	Leaky, residual splicing expected, cryptic site use may be seen at near equal amounts as WT. Increase in skipping isoform is also possible.	Created: 4.4 bit hnRNP A1 Abolished: 3.8 bit hnRNP A1 Weakened: 3.3 -> 1.0 bit TIA1	hnRNP A1 changes create opposing effects, which makes impact of ESE not predictable.	Activated cryptic donor site at position c.4664 (end of exon is c.4674, or an 10-11nt deletion)	YES
BRCA1:c.4675+3A>T (exon 14)	4.9 -> 0.4 (-4.5 bits; donor) Ri,total: 16.2 -> 11.7 bits	Pre-existing 2.8 bit site 11nt away is isoform 1: Ri,total: 13.9 bits	Natural donor abolished. Increase in skipping and cryptic site use expected.	Str: 2.2 -> 6.8 bits ELAVL1	Strengthened site would enhance splicing.	Activation of cryptic donor site 11nt away. And exon 14 skipping increase.	YES
BRCA1:c.4986+1G>C (exon 15)	3.6 -> -15.1 (-18.7 bits; donor) Ri,total: 8.4 -> -10.3 bits	Pre-existing 3.8 bit site 95nt exonic is isoform 1: Ri,total: 10.5 bits	Natural donor abolished. Increase in skipping and cryptic site use expected.	Created: 4.7 bit hnRNP A1 Abolished: 4.6 bit hnRNP A1 Str: 1.9 -> 4.8 bits (branchpoint) Str: 5.2 -> 7.1 (PTB)	hnRNP A1 changes create opposing effects, which makes impact of ESE not predictable.	Activation of cryptic site at +65 bp (intronic). This site was predicted as isoform 5, despite being the strongest cryptic donor (4.0 bits), the gap surprisal penalty was higher due to it's intronic location.	YES
BRCA1:c.5152+2dup (exon 17)	4.4 -> -5.5 (-9.5 bits; donor) Ri,total: 13.5 -> 4.0 bits	Pre-existing 1.7 bit site 16nt exonic is isoform 1: Ri,total: 11.2 bits	Natural donor abolished, so increase in skipping expected. Cryptic donor is weak, so it's use is uncertain.	Weak:4.7 -> 2.6 bits (hnRNP A1) Created: 9.8 bit TIA1 site Created: 4.3 bit ELAVL1	Including hnRNPA1 in Ri,total decreases strength further. Including TIA1 site reduces delta Ri,total, but it is still strongly negative.	Exon 17 skipping.	YES
BRCA1:c.5278-22C>G (exon 20)	14.8 -> 14.0 (-0.8 bits; acc.) Ri,total: 23.3 -> 22.5 bits	Pre-existing 8.8 bit cryptic acceptor 8nt away, not nearly as strong as weakened natural site	No significant change in splicing.	Weak: 3.0 -> 0.1 bit ELAVL1 site	Low likelihood that this ESE change would have a significant impact	Did not result in aberrant splicing.	YES
BRCA1:c.5468-1G>A (exon 23; last)	9.2 -> -1.7 (-10.9 bits; acc.) Ri,total: 6.9 -> -4.0 bits	No nearby cryptic acceptors that would lead to an Ri,total > 0 bits. Best is -0.5 bits, using a 1.2 bit cryptic acceptor 314nt exonic.	Abolishment of last exon without cryptic acceptor would likely lead to reduction of mRNA abundance due to NMD.	Created: 3.1 bit branchpoint Abolished: 2.5 bit SRp55	ESE changes not likely to be significant compared to a -1 acceptor change	A cryptic site should be created 11nt downstream of exon. Was only predicted by the acceptor model based on ~1800 sites (genome acceptor model: -2.1 bits; original acceptor model: +0.9 bits)	YES
BRCA2:c.425+415_4780dup [insGATCGCAGTGA]	Natural donor is deleted (don: 7.7 bits)	Several pre-existing cryptic sites are found within the large exon 11, including: 3.6 bit donor at c.426-209, 3.5 bit donor at c.3550 of exon 11, and a 6.4 bit donor at c.2398 (the latter with the highest Ri,total: 8.1 bits)	Loss of natural site may induce exon 11 skipping. Several cryptic donors may also be activated.	N/A	N/A	Four alternate splice forms were detected. One caused exon 11 skipping. The remainder activated 3 cryptic sites, each predicted by information theory-based tools.	YES
BRCA2:c.517G>C (exon 5)	12.7 -> 10.9 (-1.8 bits; acceptor) Ri,total: 17.4 -> 15.6 bits	No comparable cryptic acceptor in the region.	Leaky; potential increasing exon skipping splice form.	Abolished: 4.9 bit hnRNPA1 Str: 0.7 -> 4.9 bit SRp55 Weak: 6.0 -> 0.2 bit SRp40 Abolish: 3.0 -> -1.3 bit SC35	A repressor is abolished and an enhancer is created, but then two enhancers are abolished. So ESE effect is unclear.	Leads to exon skipping. Figure 4a shows that it is incomplete, Sanger sequencing shows both an exon 7 and exon 8 signal.	YES
BRCA2:c.3326C>T (exon 11)	Unaffected (don: 7.7 bits, acc. 9.3 bits) Ri,total: 6.0 bits	Cryptic donor created (4.5 bits) 3517nt from natural donor (leading to 1416nt long exon), but Ri,total is still less (-2.6 -> 4.5 bits)	Cryptic site may be seen, but would be the minority splice form compared to wildtype.	No significant changes.	No significant changes.	None affected mRNA splicing	YES
BRCA2:c.4899C>G (exon 11)	Unaffected (don: 7.7 bits, acc. 9.3 bits) Ri,total: 6.0 bits	Strengthened cryptic donor site (1.7 -> 5.6 bits) 1947 nt from natural donor (resulting exon is 2986nt long). Ri,tot: 0.1 -> 4.0 bits).	Cryptic site may be seen, but would be the minority splice form compared to wildtype.	Multiple ELAVL1 sites weakened (4.9 -> 0.6 bits, 6.8 -> 3.0 bits, 2.8 -> -0.8 bits)	These changes would only hurt the cryptic site, if they were enhancing the cryptic donor use.	None affected mRNA splicing	YES
BRCA2:c.6313A>G (exon 11)	Unaffected (don: 7.7 bits, acc. 9.3 bits) Ri,total: 6.0 bits	No information change of donor nor acceptor.	Variant doesn't change a cryptic donor or acceptor, so splicing is expecting to be unchanged.	Weak: 4.7 -> 2.9 bit TIA1	Unsure if TIA1 weakening ~200 from natural donor would have any impact on splicing.	None affected mRNA splicing	YES
BRCA2:c.6841+1G>C (exon 11)	7.7 -> -11.0 bits (-18.7 bits; donor) Ri,total: 6.1 -> -12.6 bits	Pre-existing cryptic site includes a 3.2 bit site 67nt exonic with Ri,total: 1.6 bits	Large exon 11's natural donor is abolished. No cryptic site effected. Several pre-existing splice forms are within this exon and may be activated.	Weak: 7.4 -> 2.1 bits (hnRNPH) Abolish: 3.6 (SRp55)	Abolishment of natural site would supersede any ESE changes in this region.	Skipping is most abundant aberrant splicing, but also seen is c.2398 and c.3550 splice forms, both of which are predicted, although c.3550 splice form has weak Ri,total (1.9 bits)	YES
BRCA2:c.7618-6G>T (exon 16)	6.9 -> 10.1 (+3.2 bits; acceptor) Ri,total: 6.6 -> 9.8 bits	None affected other than natural acceptor.	Greater abundance of wildtype exon, if alternate splicing existed in the region.	Abolished: 3.4 bit (hnRNP A1) Created: 3.6 bit (hnRNP A1) Created: three ELAVL1 sites (strongest is 8.3 bits)	hnRNP A1 sites "trade" (creates one, removes another), thus its effect is unknown. ELAVL1 changes would enhance wildtype exon strength.	Did not result in aberrant splicing.	YES
BRCA2:c.8488-9T>G (exon 20)	Unaffected (don: 6.6 bits; acc: -1.1 bits); Ri,total: 4.6 bits	Cryptic acceptor is created (1.3 bits) 8nt intronic, with an Ri,total of -1.0 -> 6.8 bits.	Created cryptic site is expected to be used. However, natural acceptor is -1.1 bits, which means region is likely enforced by enhancers.	Created: 4.0 bit hnRNP A1 Weakened: 4.6 -> 2.2 bits TIA1 Created: 3.2 bit SRp40 Created: 3.9 bit SF2/ASF	Several enhancers created, which may enforce created cryptic site.	Cryptic splicing leading to an out-of-frame insertion of 8nt from intron 19.	YES
BRCA2:c.8488-12A>G (exon 20)	Unaffected (don: 6.6 bits; acc: -1.1 bits); Ri,total: 4.6 bits	Pre-existing cryptic acceptor 178bp intronic is isoform #1, 4.2 bits, Ri,total is 6.2 bits	Variant doesn't affect natural or cryptic donor or acceptors, thus a change is not expected (without considering ESE impact)	Weakened: 4.6 -> 0.1 bits TIA1 Abolished: 4.2 bit PTB	Intronic TIA1 site can enhance, so it's abolishment could have an impact on natural acceptor use. But it is unknown if TIA1 site was used.	Did not result in aberrant splicing.	YES
BRCA2:c.8488-14A>G (exon 20)	Unaffected (don: 6.6 bits; acc: -1.1 bits); Ri,total: 4.6 bits	Creation of 2.8 bit site (Ri,total: -2.4 -> 8.5 bits) which would expand exon by 13nt.	Created cryptic site is expected to be used. However, natural acceptor is -1.1 bits, which means region is likely enforced by enhancers.	Strength: 4.6 -> 5.4 bits (TIA1) Created: 3.0 bits (SRp55)	Enhancers strengthened, which may enforce the cryptic or the nearby natural site.	Aberrant transcript contains out-of-frame insertion of 13nt.	YES
BRCA2:c.8954-5A>G (exon 23)	7.8 -> 7.2 bits (-0.6 bits; acceptor); Ri,total: 8.1 -> 7.5 bits	Variant simultaneously creates cryptic acceptor (0.7 -> 11.6 bits), which would make the exon 4nt longer.	Cryptic site 4nt away would be the dominant splice form, leading to frameshift. Wildtype splice form may still be detectable.	Created: 3.6 bit SRp55	Enhancer element created, which may benefit both natural and cryptic sites due to proximity.	Cryptic splicing leading to an out-of-frame insertion of 4nt from intron 22.	YES